

Voltammetric Studies of Fe(II) and Fe(III)-N-[Tris (hydroxymethyl) methyl] glycine Complexes

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The complex formation of N-[tris(hydroxymethyl) methyl glycine (Tricine) with ferrous and ferric ions has been studied voltammetrically at a rotating platinum electrode at different pH values. With ferrous ions 1:1 and 1:2 complex species were found to form with stability constants of 3.51×10^7 and 1.68×10^8 respectively. In the case of ferric ion only 1:1 complex with stability constant of 6.16×10^8 could be evaluated under the experimental conditions, although an indication for the formation of a second 1:2 complex species was obtained.

N-[TRIS(hydroxymethyl) methyl] glycine (tricine), first synthesised by Good¹, has proved quite useful as a buffer in the pH range of physiological interest^{2,3}. By E.M.F. measurements, Bates *et al.*⁴ have reported some standard thermodynamic parameters of ampholyte tricine in 50% methanol.

Tricine has a tendency to form complexes with many metal ions in which hydroxymethyl groups of the ligand can also participate in complexation. Complexometric studies of tricine with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) have been conducted by Vieles *et al.*⁵ using conductivity and potentiometric techniques. Some IR and magnetic susceptibility measurements of the solid chelates were also reported. In the authors' laboratory⁶, complex formation of tricine with some metal ions like Cd(II), Pb(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) has been investigated polarographically. These metal ions were found to form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates and at higher pH values in the alkaline range they have a tendency to form hydroxy complexes. The polarographic behaviour of Eu(III) and In(III) in tricine has also been investigated.

Systems which undergo electrochemical reactions in the anodic potential range ($>0.2V$ vs SCE) can be studied satisfactorily with the platinum electrode. The authors have used rotating platinum electrode (RPE) quite successfully in the studies of Fe(III, II)-glycine⁷, Ti(III)-glycine, Ti(III)- α -alanine and Ti(III)-N,N-dihydroxy ethylglycine complexes⁸. In the present paper voltammetric study of complexes of tricine with Fe(II) and Fe(III) is being reported, wherein RPE has been employed as the indicator electrode.

Experimental

An automatic polarograph-Radelkis type OH 102, was used for recording current-voltage curves at a scanning rate of 250 mV/minute. The working electrode consisted of a platinum wire 11.0 mm in length and

0.75 mm in diameter which was fused at the lower end of a glass tube in the direction parallel to the axis of the tube. A Sargent synchronous motor was used to rotate the electrode at a speed of 600 rpm. Electrode connections were made by filling the electrode tube with mercury. The potential values are given against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). Before recording any voltammogram, the electrode was cleaned by treating it with hot nitric acid for nearly 10 minutes and then washed thoroughly with distilled water.

The studies were carried out at different pH values in 1M KCl as supporting electrolyte. Pure nitrogen gas was used for the deaeration of the experimental solutions which were kept at a constant temperature of $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. All reagents used were of analytically pure grade. Tricine supplied by Sigma Chemical Company (USA) was used as such in the above studies.

Results

The half-wave potential values of the waves obtained for the oxidation of Fe(II) and the reduction of Fe(III) in the presence of different concentrations of tricine are given in Table 1.

The influence of change in pH value on the waves for the oxidation of Fe(II) and the reduction of Fe(III) in 50-folds excess of tricine is shown in figures 1 and 2 respectively. In case of oxidation of Fe(II), the slope of the log-plot of the wave increased with increase in pH upto pH 5 and thereafter the wave started breaking up into two. At pH 6.5, a great decrease in wave height was observed. The wave tended to disappear above pH 7. The values of log-plot analyses are given in Table 2. For the reduction of Fe(III), a tendency for the second wave to appear can be noted even at a pH value of 3.5.

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TABLE 1—VARIATION IN $E_{1/2}$ VALUES FOR Fe (II) AND Fe (III)-TRICINE SYSTEM

Fe(II) CONCN. $5 \times 10^{-4} M$, Fe(III) CONCN. $5 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Concentration of Tricine (M)	$E_{1/2}$ vs SCE for			
	Fe (II)-Tricine System at		Fe (III)-Tricine System at	
	pH 3	pH 5	pH 3	pH 9
0	+0.500	—	+0.410	—
1.25×10^{-3}	+0.495	+0.430	+0.370	—
2.50×10^{-3}	+0.480	+0.380	+0.340	-0.530
5.00×10^{-3}	+0.457	+0.332	+0.312	—
1.00×10^{-1}	+0.435	+0.285	+0.285	—
1.50×10^{-1}	—	+0.242	—	—
2.00×10^{-1}	+0.415	+0.190	+0.257	-0.535
3.00×10^{-1}	—	+0.160	—	—
4.00×10^{-1}	+0.390	+0.145	+0.230	-0.540
5.00×10^{-1}	—	+0.130	—	-0.540
6.00×10^{-1}	+0.380	—	+0.210	—

TABLE 2—LOG-PLOT ANALYSIS VALUES FOR Fe (II)-TRICINE SYSTEM

Fe (II) CONCN. $5 \times 10^{-4} M$; TRICINE CONCN. $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$.

pH	Slope	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE
2.5	0.080	+0.500
3.0	0.081	+0.480
3.5	0.110	+0.450
4.0	0.125	+0.420
4.5	0.145	+0.405
5.0	0.177	+0.380

Discussion

The Fe(II)-Fe(III) system exhibited irreversible character at the RPE in 1M KCl. For a reversible electrode reaction involving one-electron change, the slope of log-plot analysis of the wave should be nearly 0.06V. In the present case, the value of the slope for the oxidation of Fe(II) was obtained as 0.08V whereas for the reduction of Fe(III) it was found to be 0.09V, suggesting the irreversible nature of the redox system. There is a difference of about 0.09V in the $E_{1/2}$ values of the oxidation and reduction waves of iron, which also supports the above conclusion.

The Fe(II)-Fe(III) system is known to be diffusion controlled at RPE⁹. For an irreversible diffusion controlled electrode process, the change of the half-wave potential of the metal ion with ligand concentration(X) can be expressed in a simplified way as

$$E_{1/2c} = E_{1/2s} + \frac{0.06}{\alpha n} \log K_{diss} - p \frac{0.06}{\alpha n} \log [X] \quad (1)$$

at 30°C. At 1M concentration of the complexing agent this simplifies to

$$E_{1/2c} = E_{1/2s} + \frac{0.06}{\alpha n} \log K_{diss} \quad (2)$$

which can be used quite conveniently for evaluating the stability constant of the complex. The notations used have their usual significance. Here α is the transfer coefficient of the electrode process, given by

$$E = E_1 + \frac{0.06}{\alpha n} \log \frac{j_d - i}{i} \quad (3)$$

According to expression (1), for a complex species in solution, a plot between $E_{1/2c}$ and $\log [X]$ should give a straight line with a slope equal to $-p \frac{0.06}{\alpha n}$. Thus, the

Fig. 1.: Effect of pH on the oxidation waves of Fe(II)-tricine system; pH 3(A), 4(B), 5(C), 6(D), 6.5(E) and 8(F). Fe(II) concn. $5 \times 10^{-4} M$; Tricine concn. $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$

Fig. 2.: Effect of pH on the reduction waves of Fe(III)-tricine system; pH 3(A), 3.5(B), 4(C), 4.5(D), 5(E), 6(F), 7(G) and 8(H). Fe(II) concn. $5 \times 10^{-4} M$; Tricine concn. $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$

number of ligand molecules (p) attached to the metal ion can be calculated. If more than one metal-complex species are formed then in that case correspondingly more than one straight lines can be obtained and each one may be treated in the same way.

The effect of different tricine concentration on the oxidation of Fe(II) has been studied at pH 3 and 5. The influence is evident in the plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs \log [tricine] as given in figure 3.

Fig. 3.: Plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs. \log [tricine] for Fe(II)-tricine system at pH 3(O) and 5(●).

At pH 3, this plot gave a straight line, indicating the formation of one complex species. The slope of this line was found to be 0.075V and the value of α was obtained as 0.75, which gave the value of p as $0.94 \approx 1$. Thus at this pH value the formation of 1 : 1 complex is indicated.

Two separate straight lines of almost same slopes were obtained at pH 5. The first line was obtained for tricine concentration of 0.0125 to 0.100M whereas the second one was found in the concentration region of 0.200 to 0.500 M tricine. The values of the slope and α corresponding to the first straight line were 0.160V and 0.34 respectively, giving the value of p as $0.903 \approx 1$. In the case of the second curve, the α was obtained as 0.75 which is equal to that for the oxidation of simple Fe(II). The slope of the plot was 0.155V which gave the value of p as $1.94 \approx 2$. Thus at pH 5, in addition to 1 : 1, a second 1 : 2 complex between Fe(II) and tricine is also formed.

Fig. 4.: Plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs. \log [tricine] for Fe(III)-tricine system at pH 3.

Similarly, for Fe(III) system at pH 3, a straight line with a slope of 0.095V was obtained (figure 4), which gave the value of p as $1.05 \approx 1$ by using the value of α as 0.67.

For the evaluation of stability constants, the value of $E_{1/2}^0$ at ligand concentration of 1M i.e., $\log[X]=0$ can be found out from the plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log[X]$. This value together with the values of α , $E_{1/2}^0$, and n can be used in expression (2) to calculate stability constant. At the experimental pH values of 3 and 5, the value of stability constant so calculated will correspond to the apparent stability constant since at these pH values tricine does not dissociate completely. The real stability constants were obtained by multiplying the apparent stability constants by $\sum \frac{HX}{X}$ (HX =tricine) at the experimental pH values. At pH 3 and 5, the values of this quantity were obtained as 1.269×10^8 and 1.00×10^8 , using pK_1 and pK_2 values of tricine as 2.40 and 8.00 respectively. The real stability constants of different complexes are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANT VALUES

System	pH	α	p	Stability Constant
Fe (II)-Tricine	3	0.75	1	3.51×10^7
	5	0.34	1	—
	5	0.75	2	1.68×10^8
Fe (III)-Tricine	3	0.67	1	6.16×10^8

For Fe(III)-tricine system, the reduction wave started breaking up into two even at a pH value of 3.5 in 50-folds excess of tricine (0.025M). At pH values greater than 3, the wave pattern itself was found to vary with tricine concentration, even at a constant pH value. At pH values in alkaline range, again a single (although not well defined) wave was obtained. In this region, the half-wave potential value of the wave remained almost independent of the ligand concentration, as is evident from the values at pH 9 (Table 1).

Therefore, the system was studied only at pH 3 at which the formation of 1 : 1 complex species was confirmed. The system could not be studied at pH values higher than 3, for obvious reasons. The breaking up of the reduction wave into two can indicate, as in the case of Fe(II), the formation of two complex species viz. 1:1 and 1:2, although it was not possible to evaluate the second complex species of Fe(III)-tricine system under the experimental conditions.

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References

1. N. E. GOOD, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1962, 96, 653.
2. N. E. GOOD, G. D. WINGET, W. WINTER, T. N. CONNOLLY, S. IZAWA and R. M. M. SINGH, *Biochemistry*, 1966, 5, 467.
3. R. G. BATES, R. N. ROY and R. A. ROBINSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1973, 45, 1663.
4. R. G. BATES, R. N. ROY and R. A. ROBINSON, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1974, 3, 905.
5. P. VIELES, C. FREZOU, J. GALSOMIAS and A. BONNIOL, *J. Chemie Physique*, 1972, 5, 869.
6. R. C. KAPOOR, JAI KISHAN and J. K. JAILWAL, unpublished work.
7. R. C. KAPOOR and J. K. JAILWAL, *Microchem. J.*, 1971, 16, 501.
8. J.K. JAILWAL, *Ph.D. Thesis 1970*, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur, India.
9. YU. S. LYALIKOV and O. M. MUKHAMEDNAZAROVA, *Izv. Akad. Nauk. Turkm.—SSR, Ser. Fiz.—Tekhn. Khim.*, 1 Geol, Nauk, 1963, 5, 45 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1964 60, 5075